

Interval-Valued Neutrosophic Sets-Based IVNS-RAM Method for Enhanced Security Evaluation in Computer Networks

Lei Yang¹, Junyan Niu^{1*}, Jiangfeng Li²

¹Hebei Urban and Rural Construction School, Shijiazhuang, 050031, Hebei, China (E-mail: 13785176341@163.com)

²College of Science, Jiujiang University, Jiujiang, 332005, Jiangxi, China (E-mail: jiangfengli2000@163.com; jiangfengli2000@jju.edu.cn)

*Corresponding author, E-mail: 16603115775@163.com

Abstract: Computer network security (CNS) evaluation is the process of analyzing and assessing the security of a network system. Its goal is to identify potential security vulnerabilities and threats, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the network. The process typically includes risk assessment, vulnerability scanning, penetration testing, and security policy review. Through these measures, organizations can develop effective security strategies and implement appropriate security controls to prevent data breaches, network attacks, and other security incidents, thereby protecting the security of information assets. The evaluation of CNS is multiple-attribute group decision-making (MAGDM). Recently, the Root Assessment Method (RAM) approach was elucidated to cope with MAGDM. The interval-valued neutrosophic sets (IVNSs) are elucidated as a decision tool for characterizing fuzzy data during the evaluation of CNS. In this study, the interval-valued neutrosophic number combined RAM (IVNN-RAM) approach is elucidated to solve the MAGDM under IVNSs. Conclusively, a numerical study for evaluation of CNS is elucidated to elucidate the IVNN-RAM approach through comparative analysis.

Keywords: Multiple-attribute group decision-making (MAGDM); IVNSs; Root Assessment Method (RAM); Computer network security (CNS) evaluation

1. Introduction

Computer network security evaluation is the process of comprehensively analyzing and assessing the security of network systems to identify potential threats and vulnerabilities and propose improvements. With the rapid development of information technology, network security issues have become increasingly complex, and traditional evaluation methods struggle to address the diverse threats in modern network environments. Therefore, recent research has focused on developing more advanced security evaluation techniques. These techniques include the use of artificial intelligence

and machine learning algorithms, such as neural networks and support vector machines, to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of security evaluations. Additionally, methods like fuzzy comprehensive evaluation and analytic hierarchy process are applied to handle complex multi-factor decision-making problems. By quantifying network security risks, these methods help organizations better understand their security posture and formulate effective security strategies. In summary, computer network security evaluation is a crucial tool for ensuring the security of information systems. It not only helps identify and mitigate potential threats but also guides the development and implementation of security strategies, thereby enhancing overall network security. The field of computer network security evaluation has evolved significantly over the years, with various methodologies being explored and developed to address the ever-growing challenges of cybersecurity. This summary provides an overview of the research from 2017 to 2024, highlighting key advancements and methodologies proposed in the literature. In 2017, Mi and Wu [1] focused on the application of neural networks in computer network security evaluation. They analyzed the use of index sets, model building, and implementation to optimize neural networks, aiming to enhance network security. Their work laid the foundation for subsequent research in utilizing artificial intelligence for cybersecurity purposes. By 2018, several researchers had expanded on this foundation. Wang [2] explored the use of support vector regression machines in security evaluation, addressing the limitations of traditional linear evaluation methods. He proposed a novel approach to strengthen the evaluation of security indices, which was crucial for adapting to the complex and dynamic nature of cyber threats. Simultaneously, Wang [3] investigated the application of the fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (AHP) in security evaluations. This method aimed to overcome the low accuracy of linear evaluation techniques, offering a more nuanced approach to assessing network security risks. Xu [4] made significant strides by integrating BP neural networks and genetic algorithms (GA) to form the GABP neural network model. This model was applied to computer network security evaluation, demonstrating effective results and showcasing the potential of hybrid models in cybersecurity. Liu [5] also contributed by emphasizing the need for security evaluation methods that minimize human interference and have broad applicability. His work on the GABP neural network algorithm highlighted the importance of robust and adaptable evaluation techniques in rapidly evolving network environments. Zhang [6] addressed the challenges posed by the big data era, evaluating the effectiveness of existing network information security measures. She identified several deficiencies and provided recommendations for optimization, stressing the need for improved data protection strategies in an era of massive data proliferation. Wei [7] focused on the layered evaluation protection system, highlighting the importance of comprehensive defense mechanisms in safeguarding network security. Her research underscored the necessity of developing multi-layered security frameworks to address increasingly sophisticated cyber threats. In 2019, Ma [8] evaluated the role of data encryption technology in enhancing network security. She explored methods to bolster security through encryption, recognizing its critical role in protecting sensitive information

from unauthorized access and cyberattacks. Wei [9] further advanced the field by examining the construction of layered evaluation systems. He provided insights into building more complete and scientifically grounded evaluation frameworks, which are essential for ensuring long-term security and stability in network environments. By 2021, Jiang and Ye [10] discussed the critical role of layered evaluation protection systems in promoting network development. They emphasized that robust security frameworks are key to fostering innovation and growth in digital infrastructures. Finally, in 2024, Zhuang [11] proposed an integrated approach combining the analytic hierarchy process and fuzzy comprehensive evaluation for network security management. She developed a comprehensive evaluation system that identified training management as a high-risk area, highlighting the need for continuous improvement in personnel training to mitigate risks effectively. In conclusion, the evolution of computer network security evaluation from 2017 to 2024 reflects a growing sophistication in methodologies and a deeper understanding of the complexities involved in protecting digital infrastructures. The integration of advanced algorithms, such as neural networks and fuzzy logic, alongside traditional evaluation methods, has paved the way for more robust and adaptive security frameworks. These advancements underscore the importance of continuous research and innovation in the face of ever-evolving cyber threats.

The evaluation of CNS is MAGDM. Recently, the LogTODIM approach [12, 13] was elucidated to put forward MAGDM. The IVNSs [14] are elucidated as a decision tool for characterizing fuzzy data during the evaluation of CNS.

RAM is a new MCDM technique that aggregates the scores of each option across decision criteria to get its utility value. The overall ranking is then determined based on these utility values. RAM uses a straightforward but effective aggregating function to accomplish this, which is inversely proportional to the effect produced by all non-beneficial criteria and directly proportionate to the effect produced by all beneficial criteria. Actually, the foundation of RAM is an aggregating function that consistently and informatively blends the compensatory and partially compensatory properties. The following presumption underlies the construction of RAM's aggregating function: -The level of compensation varies between beneficial and non-beneficial criteria. A new level of compensation between these criteria actually exists, which is uncommon in literature [15-18].

In this study, the IVNN-RAM approach is elucidated to put forward MAGDM under IVNSs. Conclusively, a numerical study for evaluation of CNS is elucidated to validate the IVNN-RAM through comparative analysis. The major research motivations of this study are elucidated: (1) IVNN-RAM approach is elucidated to put forward the MAGDM for IVNN; (2) Conclusively, a numerical study for evaluation of CNS is elucidated and (3) sensitivity analysis was applied.

The basic structure of this study is elucidated. In Sect. 2, the IVNSs are elucidated. In Sect. 3, the IVNN-RAM approach is elucidated for MAGDM for IVNSs. Sect. 4 elucidates

a numerical study for evaluation of CNS through comparative analysis. Final remarks are elucidated in Sect. 5.

2. Preliminaries

This section includes some definitions of IVNSs [19-22].

Definition 1.

The neutrosophic set can be presented as:

$$Y = \{(T_Y(u_i), I_Y(u_i), F_Y(u_i) | u_i \in U)\} \quad (1)$$

Definition 2.

The IVNS can be defined as:

$$T_Y(u_i) = [\inf T_Y(u), \sup T_Y(u)] \quad (2)$$

$$I_Y(u_i) = [\inf I_Y(u), \sup I_Y(u)] \quad (3)$$

$$F_Y(u_i) = [\inf F_Y(u), \sup F_Y(u)] \quad (4)$$

$$Y = \{[\inf T_Y(u), \sup T_Y(u)], [\inf I_Y(u), \sup I_Y(u)], [\inf F_Y(u), \sup F_Y(u)]\} \quad (5)$$

Definition 3.

Let a and b are IVNNs such as:

$$a = \{[\inf T_a(u), \sup T_a(u)], [\inf I_a(u), \sup I_a(u)], [\inf F_a(u), \sup F_a(u)]\} \quad (6)$$

$$b = \{[\inf T_b(u), \sup T_b(u)], [\inf I_b(u), \sup I_b(u)], [\inf F_b(u), \sup F_b(u)]\} \quad (7)$$

$$a + b = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\inf T_a(u) + \inf T_b(u) - \inf T_a(u) \inf T_b(u), \\ \sup T_a(u) + \sup T_b(u) - \sup T_a(u) \sup T_b(u)] \\ [\inf I_a(u) \inf I_b(u), \sup I_a(u) \sup I_b(u)], \\ [\inf F_a(u) \inf F_b(u), \sup F_a(u) \sup F_b(u)] \end{array} \right\} \quad (8)$$

$$ab = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\inf T_a(u) \inf T_b(u), \sup T_a(u) \sup T_b(u)], \\ [\inf I_a(u) + \inf I_b(u) - \inf I_a(u) \inf I_b(u), \\ \sup I_a(u) + \sup I_b(u) - \sup I_a(u) \sup I_b(u)] \\ [\inf F_a(u) + \inf F_b(u) - \inf F_a(u) \inf F_b(u), \\ \sup F_a(u) + \sup F_b(u) - \sup F_a(u) \sup F_b(u)] \end{array} \right\} \quad (9)$$

Definition 4.

The score function can be computed as:

$$S(x) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\inf T_a(u) + \sup T_a(u)}{2} + \\ \left(1 - \frac{(\inf I_a(u) + \sup I_a(u))}{2}\right) \times (\sup I_a(u)) - \\ \left(\frac{(\inf F_a(u) + \sup F_a(u))}{2}\right) \times (1 - \sup F_a(u)) \end{array} \right\} \quad (10)$$

Figure 1. The steps of the IVNS-RAM.

3. INN-RAM approach for MAGDM

This section presents the steps of the IVV-RAM methodology to compute the criteria weights and rank the alternatives. Figure 1 shows the steps of the RAM methodology.

1. Build the decision matrix

The decision matrix is built by using the opinions of experts.

$$T_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} t_{11} & \cdots & t_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ t_{m1} & \cdots & t_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

2. Then these opinions are replaced by using interval-valued neutrosophic numbers.

3. Then we applied the score function to obtain the crisp values.

4. Then we combined the decision matrix

5. Then we compute the criteria weights.

The criteria weights are obtained using the average method

6. Normalize the decision matrix

The decision matrix is normalized using the linear sum normalization method.

$$N_{ij} = \frac{t_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m t_{ij}} \quad (12)$$

Where $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$

7. Compute the weighted normalized decision matrix

$$e_{ij} = w_j N_{ij} \quad (13)$$

8. Calculate the sum of the weighted normalized decision matrix.

This operation is computed for the positive and negative criteria.

$$R_{+i} = \sum_{j=1}^n q_{+ij} \quad (14)$$

$$R_{-i} = \sum_{j=1}^n q_{-ij} \quad (15)$$

9. Calculate the overall score

$$U_i = \frac{2+R_{+i}}{\sqrt{2+R_{+i}}} \quad (16)$$

10. Rank the alternatives

4. Case Study

Computer network security evaluation is a comprehensive process of analyzing and assessing the security of a network system, with the core objective of ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the network. This process typically involves several steps, including risk assessment, vulnerability scanning, penetration testing, and security policy review. Risk assessment helps identify and prioritize potential threats and vulnerabilities that may impact network security. Vulnerability scanning uses specialized software tools to detect known vulnerabilities within the network. Penetration testing simulates the behavior of attackers to discover security weaknesses in the system. Security policy review checks whether existing security measures and policies are effective and compliant with industry standards. Through these comprehensive measures, organizations can identify security blind spots, develop and implement more effective security strategies and controls to prevent data breaches, network attacks, and other security incidents, thereby protecting the security of information assets. This process not only enhances the network's defense capabilities but also improves the response to potential security events. The evaluation of CNS is MAGDM. Therefore, the evaluation of CNS is elucidated to demonstrate the INN-RAM approach. Eight possible CNS systems are evaluated in light with INNs through 12 attributes and three experts. Table 1 shows the criteria.

- 1-4. We invited three experts to evaluate the criteria and alternatives and build the decision matrix. Then we replaced their opinions by using the IVNNs. Then we applied the score function to obtain crisp values. Then we combined the decision matrix
5. Figure 2 shows the criteria for weights.
6. Eq. (12) is used to normalize the decision matrix as displayed in Table 2.
7. Then we used Eq. (13) to compute the weighted normalized decision matrix as displayed in Table 3.
8. All criteria are positive, we used Eq. (14) to calculate the sum of the weighted normalized decision matrix.
9. Eq. (16) is used to calculate the overall score
10. We ranked the alternatives as displayed in Figure 3.

Table 1. The 12 attributes in this study.

Number	Attributes
C ₁	Risk Assessment
C ₂	Vulnerability Scanning
C ₃	Penetration Testing
C ₄	Access Control
C ₅	Encryption Measures
C ₆	Intrusion Detection System
C ₇	Security Policy Review
C ₈	Network Traffic Monitoring
C ₉	Patch Management
C ₁₀	User Authentication
C ₁₁	Data Backup and Recovery
C ₁₂	Log and Event Management

Table 2. The normalized decision matrix

	A ₁	A ₂	A ₃	A ₄	A ₅	A ₆	A ₇	A ₈
C ₁	0.116347	0.105088	0.133028	0.144287	0.119266	0.116764	0.110926	0.154295
C ₂	0.115133	0.126685	0.142857	0.115133	0.127455	0.142857	0.122449	0.107432
C ₃	0.138691	0.123432	0.138013	0.085453	0.130214	0.111563	0.133944	0.138691
C ₄	0.12975	0.137966	0.137966	0.074974	0.14584	0.118453	0.118453	0.136597
C ₅	0.121075	0.154222	0.134334	0.091417	0.130844	0.124215	0.15492	0.088974
C ₆	0.110209	0.135344	0.137664	0.117943	0.126063	0.104408	0.155839	0.112529
C ₇	0.115705	0.149438	0.070366	0.125861	0.154878	0.143272	0.126224	0.114255
C ₈	0.123926	0.112106	0.12106	0.137178	0.135745	0.145415	0.105659	0.118911
C ₉	0.138636	0.082955	0.120455	0.160227	0.117045	0.160227	0.095076	0.125379
C ₁₀	0.105541	0.098756	0.104033	0.16585	0.105541	0.101772	0.137957	0.18055
C ₁₁	0.127454	0.116431	0.152256	0.13331	0.112642	0.127799	0.109542	0.120565
C ₁₂	0.163326	0.1585	0.165553	0.088344	0.097253	0.122123	0.086488	0.118411

Table 3. The weighted normalized decision matrix

	A ₁	A ₂	A ₃	A ₄	A ₅	A ₆	A ₇	A ₈
C ₁	0.008518	0.007693	0.009739	0.010563	0.008731	0.008548	0.008121	0.011296
C ₂	0.009128	0.010044	0.011326	0.009128	0.010105	0.011326	0.009708	0.008518
C ₃	0.012486	0.011112	0.012425	0.007693	0.011723	0.010044	0.012059	0.012486
C ₄	0.01157	0.012303	0.012303	0.006686	0.013005	0.010563	0.010563	0.012181
C ₅	0.010593	0.013494	0.011754	0.007999	0.011448	0.010868	0.013555	0.007785
C ₆	0.008701	0.010685	0.010868	0.009311	0.009952	0.008243	0.012303	0.008884
C ₇	0.009739	0.012578	0.005923	0.010593	0.013036	0.012059	0.010624	0.009617
C ₈	0.010563	0.009556	0.010319	0.011693	0.01157	0.012395	0.009006	0.010136
C ₉	0.011174	0.006686	0.009708	0.012914	0.009433	0.012914	0.007663	0.010105
C ₁₀	0.008548	0.007999	0.008426	0.013433	0.008548	0.008243	0.011174	0.014623
C ₁₁	0.011296	0.010319	0.013494	0.011815	0.009983	0.011326	0.009708	0.010685
C ₁₂	0.013433	0.013036	0.013616	0.007266	0.007999	0.010044	0.007113	0.009739

Figure 2. The criteria weights.

Figure 3. The rank of alternatives.

4.1. Sensitivity Analysis

This part shows the different ranks of alternatives under different weights. We change the criteria weights with 12 cases as shown in Table 4. In the first scenario, we put all criteria with equal weight. In the second scenario, we put the first and second criterion with 0.1 weight and other cases with the same weights. Then we applied the RAM method under different criteria weights. We show the rank of alternatives as shown in Figure 4. We show the stability of the rank and alternative 4 is the best and alternative 3 is the worst.

Table 4. The different weights.

	R ₁	R ₁	R ₁	R ₁	R ₁	R ₁	R ₁	R ₁	R ₁	R ₁	R ₁	R ₁
C ₁	0.083333	0.1	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
C ₂	0.083333	0.1	0.1	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
C ₃	0.083333	0.08	0.1	0.1	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
C ₄	0.083333	0.08	0.08	0.1	0.1	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
C ₅	0.083333	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.1	0.1	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
C ₆	0.083333	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.1	0.1	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
C ₇	0.083333	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.1	0.1	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
C ₈	0.083333	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.1	0.1	0.08	0.08	0.08
C ₉	0.083333	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.1	0.1	0.08	0.08
C ₁₀	0.083333	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.1	0.1	0.08
C ₁₁	0.083333	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.1	0.1
C ₁₂	0.083333	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.1

Figure 4. The different ranks.

4.2 Managerial Implications

In the context of computer network security evaluation, ensuring the safety and integrity of network operations is a top priority for managers overseeing these systems. The use of Neutrosophic Theory, specifically IVNS, provides a powerful tool for decision-making in the context of uncertain and imprecise data, which is common in risk assessments for network security operations NSO. For managers, the application of the IVNN-RAM approach can significantly improve the accuracy and reliability of risk evaluations by accounting for both known and unknown risks in a comprehensive, transparent way.

Managers can use this methodology to make more informed decisions about network security and risk management. By considering multiple attributes and decision-making factors, managers can identify potential security vulnerabilities and operational inefficiencies more effectively. This approach also helps in prioritizing security measures, allocating resources where they are most needed, and responding proactively to potential risks, ultimately leading to safer, more efficient network systems.

Furthermore, adopting Neutrosophic-based risk assessment tools allows managers to deal with uncertainty and incomplete information in a structured manner, enhancing overall decision-making processes in environments where data is often uncertain or fuzzy. By leveraging this advanced decision-making framework, managers can better navigate complex, high-stakes situations, ensuring that network systems operate safely and efficiently, even under uncertain conditions.

4.3 Importance of Introducing Neutrosophic Theory

The introduction of Neutrosophic Theory into the field of risk assessment for computer network security is particularly important because it addresses inherent uncertainty and complexity in real-world decision-making. Traditional decision-making methods often struggle when faced with vague, conflicting, or incomplete data—common scenarios in network security operations. Neutrosophic Theory offers a way to capture and process this uncertainty, allowing for more nuanced and comprehensive assessments.

In the context of network security risk assessment, Neutrosophic Theory helps to represent various types of uncertainty—such as data imprecision, lack of information, or contradictory factors—without forcing decision-makers into rigid, oversimplified models. This flexibility is crucial when assessing the security of network operations, where conditions may change rapidly or data may not be fully available.

The IVNSs framework, in particular, helps to model this uncertainty in a way that allows for better handling of complex decision-making situations. By integrating this approach into risk assessments, network security systems can identify hidden vulnerabilities, improve security protocols, and optimize resource allocation even when faced with incomplete or contradictory information. For network managers and decision-makers, this means having a more accurate, adaptable, and reliable method to guide risk management strategies, ultimately leading to more resilient and secure network systems that can effectively protect against various cyber threats.

5. Conclusion

Computer network security evaluation is a comprehensive analysis of network systems aimed at identifying potential security vulnerabilities and threats, and assessing their impact on an organization. This process typically includes several steps such as risk identification, vulnerability scanning, penetration testing, and security policy review. Risk identification is the initial phase, focused on determining internal and external threats that could affect network security. Next, vulnerability scanning uses automated tools to detect known vulnerabilities in the system. Penetration testing assesses the system's defenses by simulating attacks to uncover unrecognized security weaknesses. Access control and encryption measures are critical factors in network security evaluation, ensuring that only authorized users can access sensitive data and that data integrity and confidentiality are maintained through encryption technologies. Additionally, intrusion detection systems (IDS) and network traffic monitoring tools are used to monitor network activities in real-time, enabling the timely detection and response to abnormal behaviors. Security policy review is a necessary step to ensure that an organization's security policies and procedures are effective and comply with industry standards. By regularly updating patches and software, organizations can mitigate risks associated with known vulnerabilities. User authentication mechanisms prevent unauthorized access by verifying user identities. Overall, computer network security evaluation is not only a collection of technical measures but also includes management strategies and user education to establish a comprehensive security framework that protects an organization's information assets from potential cyber-attacks. The evaluation of CNS is MAGDM. Currently, the RAM approach was elucidated to put forward the MAGDM. The IVNSs are elucidated as a decision tool

for characterizing fuzzy data during the evaluation of CNS. In this study, the IVNN-RAM approach is elucidated to solve the MAGDM under IVNSs. Conclusively, a numerical study for evaluation of CNS is elucidated to validate the IVNN-RAM approach through comparative analysis.

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